

Unlocking Employer Insights: Leveraging Large Language Models to Explore Human-Centric Aspects in the Context of Industry 5.0

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Abstract

This paper aims to contribute to Industry 5.0's understanding by setting up an innovative AI-based methodology that identifies employer expressions in job postings to the well-being (human-centricity) concept. This process involves creating a comprehensive dictionary cross-validated against academia, enabling empirical well-being analysis from employers' perspectives. Bridging theoretical and practical realms, we offer valuable insights to academia and industry about human-centricity's interpretation by employers. Additionally, we tackle the intricacies of mapping employee well-being terms within workplace contexts using job vacancy data. Our findings highlight employers' prioritisation of self-realisation and a positive work atmosphere to attract job seekers. Nonetheless, most employers do not explicitly emphasise well-being to attract potential workers.

JEL Classification: J28, J63, L23, L86, O33

Keywords: Industry 5.0, job vacancies, LLM, well-being, human-centricity

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1 Introduction

The arrival of Industry 5.0, frequently referred to as the fifth industrial revolution, has introduced a fresh wave of new ideas to the industrial landscape. In contrast to Industry 4.0, which predominantly emphasised productivity gains, Industry 5.0 shifts the focus towards a more holistic approach. As highlighted by the European Commission (2023), there are three main pillars that are supposed to be at the centre of Industry 5.0: human-centricity, sustainability and resilience. The paradigm recognises the significance of human involvement and aims to balance upcoming technologies and human-centric considerations. By prioritising human well-being and meaningful interactions, Industry 5.0 endeavours to create a harmonious coexistence between humans and machines, fostering a more sustainable and inclusive industrial landscape (Xu et al., 2021; Leng et al., 2022; Kolade and Owoseni, 2022).

However, as Industry 5.0 gains momentum, the challenge of analysing this phenomenon lies in the absence of a clear understanding of what the major pillars of Industry 5.0 refer to and how to measure them empirically. Solely focusing on the concept of human-centricity begs the question of human-centricity according to who? One perspective is academia, where researchers emphasise exploring various aspects of human-robot collaboration, human-cyber interaction, and well-being at the workplace (Leng et al., 2022; Shiroishi et al., 2018). Another one is that of employees, who value their personal lives, relationships, and well-being outside of work as they seek environments that support their ability to maintain this balance. Lastly, there is the perspective of an employer who recognises the importance of having motivated and productive employees to foster growth and success for both the individuals and the company.

Among these diverse perspectives, well-being emerges as a common ground that can connect all stakeholders. Significant efforts have already been delivered from academia to conceptualise and showcase workplace well-being strategies from a

theoretical standpoint (Ghobakhloo et al., 2023). However, limited attention has been given to studying the well-being aspect of human-centricity from the perspectives of employees and employers, mainly due to the dynamic nature of the phenomenon and the challenges associated with collecting and analysing up-to-date data (Mytna Kurekova et al., 2014). As a result, there exists a research niche that can be further explored.

Acquiring and measuring data from multiple perspectives presents challenges. Traditionally, researchers have used quantitative and qualitative methods, like surveys and interviews, to map job characteristics and understand labour requirements. Text mining techniques have recently been explored to extract information from large datasets such as job postings and resumes. However, text mining's focus on extracting patterns from textual data may not accurately capture nuanced context and subtleties, leading to potential misinterpretations and irrelevant information. These issues can significantly impact the pattern identification process and analysis outcomes (Vijayarani et al., 2015; Gaikwad et al., 2014).

Fortunately, the most recent LLMs presented by OpenAI in 2022 and 2023 (Chatgpt 3.5 and GPT-4) have set a new milestone of what Artificial Intelligence algorithms can achieve. The sophisticated embedding mechanisms of transformers can capture the nuances of the text, reason accordingly and infer when directed. Facebook Large Language Model Meta AI (LLaMa) weights have been open-sourced in 2023 for public use. As a result, an unlimited potential of new natural language processing techniques has been unlocked that can be applied to the labour market, such as well-being analysis.

Thus, through our research, we seek to contribute to the knowledge and understanding of Industry 5.0 by presenting a novel AI-based approach. We aim to build an automatic pattern recognition system/algorithm that relates the well-being concept to employers' expressions posted in job vacancies. In this process, we create a comprehensive dictionary of employer expressions, which we cross-validate with the academic perspective. This unique approach enables us to empirically analyse

the well-being aspect of human-centricity from the employer’s standpoint. Our research aims to bridge the gap between theoretical concepts and practical applications, offering valuable insights to both academia and industry regarding the interpretation of human-centricity from the perspective of employers. Moreover, we address the challenges associated with measuring and mapping the intricate terms linked to employee well-being in the workplace using vacancy data.

Given the data-intensive nature of LLMs’ training requirements, the emphasis was placed on exploring the employer’s perspective, using the abundant data readily accessible through job search platforms. As a result, this paper uses over 1.8 million job posts collected from the UK. We have deployed a fine-tuned LLM for the job posting text to capture a particular aspect of human-centricity. More specifically, while browsing the job postings, we have identified that certain employers express a large variety of benefits for an employee’s well-being. These benefits include but are not limited to health benefits like mental health support, welfare, generous pension schemes, autonomy and much more. These well-being benefits directly contribute to a worker’s overall well-being and happiness and thus should be considered as one of the requirements for achieving human-centricity within the workplace (Sirgy, 2018). After mining the benefit phraseology, data were further processed to conceptualise a detailed empirical image of what should be considered in a workplace striving to become an empowering incubator for workers’ life and work satisfaction from an employers’ perspective. Furthermore, we conducted a well-being conceptual search on academic Industry 5.0 literature, resulting in 89 well-being-related phrases. The latter findings were cross-validated with employers’ perspectives to highlight the overlaps and gaps between perspectives.

Our contribution is two-fold. First, we propose a novel methodological approach for concept extraction applicable across various domains. Secondly, we offer a structured perspective on well-being, focusing on employers’ and industry 5.0 academic literature viewpoint and their perceptions of employee welfare. With the results, we can support organisations, policymakers, and educational institutions

in navigating the job requirements landscape of the fifth industrial revolution.

The paper proceeds with a background section (Section 2). The methodology employed to identify well-being patterns in job vacancies is outlined in Section 3. Section 4 showcases the mapping results, followed by a comprehensive discussion in Section 5. The final section concludes.

2 Background

2.1 Previous research on well-being

Academia has already started pursuing the well-being aspects of human-centricity. Authors strongly emphasise that future technologies should be implemented to maximise workers' health, safety, satisfaction and performance at the workplace (Papetti et al., 2020; Alves et al., 2023). As discussed by Alves et al. (2023), strategies to create a human-centric should involve motivating and rewarding work, as well as safe and inclusive environments, that put much emphasis on workers' physical and mental health, dignity, autonomy, privacy and well-being (Orso et al., 2022). Other strategies to improve worker well-being were suggested through job rotation, diversity of work schedule times, considering the demands of getting the job done and ergonomic workplace exposure (Khamaisi et al., 2022). Thus, in the foreseeable future, the industry must shift from technological to socio-technological working environments where workers continue to acquire, upgrade and retain skills to better their career prospects while keeping the work-life balance in check (Brauner and Ziefle, 2022; Alves et al., 2023).

Certainly, the academic perspective provides a solid foundation for the direction of human-centricity and well-being. However, it is equally important to consider viewpoints from an employee and employer perspectives and how they understand the well-being at the work-place. Unfortunately, such viewpoints explicitly mentioning human-centricity are scarce, as most of the well-being literature comes

from domains like psychology, human resources, health sciences and other related domains. Nonetheless, empirical research suggests that balance between work and non-work strongly impacts a person's motivation, productivity, happiness and fulfilment at the workplace (Sirgy, 2018). An interview with 61 IT professionals concluded that interpersonal relationships, fulfilling work, feeling safe and valued, and having colleague support is a big part of well-being (Zutavern and Seifried, 2021). Other studies have found a strong relationship between measures of job control and health (Spell and Arnold, 2007; Karasek, 1990). In a study of 8,500 white-collar workers in Sweden who had undergone reorganisations, it was discovered that those who had more task control and influence over the process had lower levels of illness symptoms for 11 out of 12 health indicators, missed fewer days of work, and suffered from less depression (Karasek, 1990).

Moreover, an extensive review of 39 randomised controlled studies has outlined eight successful interventions that improve the workers' well-being (Sakuraya A., 2022). For instance, environmental intervention had shown an improvement in evaluative worker well-being when communication, workflow and health services were improved. Likewise, physical intervention, where participating in yoga or other sports, has resulted in better worker mental health. Furthermore, a study involving focus groups on the employers' side found unanimous agreement among owners that occupational safety is paramount. Other important aspects were mental support, colleague support, and work-life-family balance (Pescud et al., 2015).

Despite existing studies on well-being, there are still considerable drawbacks that must be accounted for. First, the existing studies have limited sample analysis, as interviews and surveys are costly. This limits our comprehensive understanding, as some important factors might be omitted. Second, few studies delve into the perception of workers' well-being from an employer's eye. Fortunately, with the age of digitisation, many employers signal their intentions and priorities through social media channels and other platforms, which has the potential for scientific research as it allows for analysing and examining employer's signalling strategies.

2.2 Recent advancements and limitations on data mining

Machine learning, text mining techniques and online sources of information have proven to be valuable tools in analysing and extracting information from text data such as job vacancy postings. Regrettably, we are yet to witness text mining approaches to be developed for the well-being concepts using online data. However, significant research in other domains has proven to deliver useful results when incorporating web data. For instance, Pejic-Bach et al. (2020) used vacancy data and text mining techniques to develop a profile of Industry 4.0 job advertisements. Likewise, a paper by Chiarello et al. (2021) deployed text mining to classify Industry 4.0 and ESCO skills. Successful attempts have also been reported by Meganck et al. (2021), who analysed 1,000 job positions to extract skills that concerned public relations advertisements. Thielen and Marsolek (2022) investigated 50 job postings for the librarian positions while Gardiner et al. (2017) analysed 2,786 job advertisements that contained "big data" in the job title to capture the requirements.

Nonetheless, it is important to acknowledge the existing studies' limitations when identifying patterns in a text. One of the main challenges is the reliance on the quality and quantity of the training data used to train the machine learning models. Insufficient or biased training data can lead to inaccurate or incomplete pattern recognition (Chiarello et al., 2021; Pejic-Bach et al., 2020). For instance, Pejic-Bach et al. (2020) used vacancy data and text mining techniques to develop a profile of Industry 4.0 job advertisements. Firstly, the relatively low number of job vacancies (1,460 job advertisements) may not comprehensively represent all jobs and their associated characteristics. Secondly, the text-mining techniques employed in the study have the potential to introduce biases. Specifically, the chosen techniques may overlook important phrases or patterns of interest, as text mining focuses on specific patterns and variations in the wording used by employers or the inclusion of synonyms to describe job characteristics. Additionally, these techniques may struggle with understanding human language's context, subtleties,

and nuances, making it challenging to capture complex patterns accurately (Qaiser and Ali, 2018; Vijayarani et al., 2016). The dynamic nature of language and the evolving use of slang, jargon, and cultural references pose difficulties for these techniques.

2.3 Exploring Solutions with LLMs for the well-being

Although there have been recent improvements in text mining and advanced machine learning methods, a comprehensive data science approach to the concept of well-being has not yet been fully developed. As of now, we can generalise that this research gap stems from two primary factors. Firstly, there is a lack of attempts to quantify the employer perspective using online data. Secondly, the conventional pattern-matching algorithms employed in previous research fall short in extracting more nuanced and ambiguous concepts, as it requires a clear alphabetic letter pattern. On the contrary, well-being analysis requires pattern recognition and conceptual recognition. The latter has a much higher dimensional search space since well-being expression can take many forms.

Despite severe challenges, the latest LLMs might hold the key to addressing the latter issues. Unlike previous NLP techniques, LLMs work by being trained on vast amounts of text from diverse sources, such as books, articles, websites, and other textual data. This training allows LLMs to learn the statistical patterns and relationships between words and phrases (Zhao et al., 2023). LLMs, such as GPT-3, have demonstrated impressive capabilities in natural language processing and understanding context. They can analyse and generate human-like text, which makes them well-suited for extracting and comprehending complex information from diverse sources, including job postings, resumes, and other labour market data. Moreover, LLMs can capture the nuanced relationships between words and phrases, enabling them to recognise variations and synonyms (Wang and Cho, 2015). Their ability to generate coherent and contextually appropriate responses

allows for more accurate job characteristics identification.

More recently, GPT-4 was tested on a series of MIT math exams, which were passed with a 100% accuracy. The latter is another indication of the superiority of LLMs against previous NLP techniques and their ability to understand conceptual paradigms (Zhang et al., 2023b). However, since the revolution of LLMs has only begun in November 2022, the literature surrounding LLMs and their applicability to the labour market domain is relatively scarce. Thus, within the realm of this paper, it is worthy of attempting to explore its potential.

3 Methodology

3.1 Data

To achieve a comprehensive understanding of the well-being aspect, substantial data is required. As a result, we have established a data pipeline for data collection, as depicted in Figure 1.

DC-301. First, an Ubuntu server was configured with a plethora of web-scraping scripts to collect data from various publicly available online sources. The server ran continuously 24/7, and scraping was initiated from daily to weekly timetables, depending on the source.

DC-302. A reliable data source is most important for successful data modelling results. As the saying goes, “garbage in, garbage out” will not be solved by machine learning methods; thus, trustworthy data is vital (Weyerer and Langer, 2019). As a result, it was decided to choose UK online job platforms as they serve as a hub where employers post job listings that provide comprehensive details, including job titles, working conditions, salary information, required qualifications and experience (Cárdenas Rubio, 2020; Cedefop, 2019; Barnes et al., 2021; Mytna Kurekova et al., 2014; Turrell et al., 2018, among others). The UK has high internet penetration and adoption, making it a hub for online activities (ONS, 2020). As a result,

its array of job portals offers broad coverage of the diverse job landscape within its economy. Moreover, the UK is a developed country that has been actively embracing the concept of Industry 4.0 (integration of advanced digital technologies, automation, data analytics, and the Internet of Things, etc.) (ITA, 2022; BEIS, 2020; Oztemel and Gursev, 2020). This positioning makes the UK an intriguing case study to explore the transition from Industry 4.0 to the more advanced Industry 5.0.

The UK vacancy data was collected throughout the year 2022, from January to December. The information was downloaded monthly by “web scraping” selected job portals, automating the searching and downloading of the data. The job portals were selected based on the number of job advertisements, website quality (structure and the number of variables or granularity of information), and traffic ranking¹. As the information was collected, different methods were utilised to standardise and categorise the vacancy data. These methods can be summarised as follows (Cárdenas Rubio, 2020):

DC-303. Text Cleaning and Preprocessing: Raw text data obtained from web scraping underwent thorough cleaning, including removing HTML tags, special characters, and irrelevant content, to ensure accurate analysis. Data from different portals were integrated into a unified database structure. Columns and data types were aligned across different sources to ensure consistency in the database structure. Moreover, Values that represent the same information but are formatted differently were standardised (e.g., “Full-Time” and “FT”). Given that, in principle, employers might post the same vacancy several times in the same or different job portals, duplicate vacancies are discarded. Duplicates are identified amongst vacancy announcements with the same job title, experience needs, educational requirements, localisation, wages, year, month, etc.

DC-304. After each collection and structuring, the data was stored in the SQL

¹It’s worth noting that this diversified selection of job portals was aimed at mitigating potential biases associated with focusing solely on a particular subset of occupations.

Figure 1: Data collection pipeline

database within the server.

In the end, the final data set consisted of over 1.8 million observations. As discussed by different authors (Mytna Kurekova et al., 2014; Cárdenas Rubio, 2020; Napierala et al., 2022, among others), even though job portal information contains a considerable amount of data, this does not guarantee that this information is representative of the whole number of vacancies available economy. Given the nature of job portals, these sources might not sufficiently represent the agriculture sector or informal jobs. However, in the UK, the size of these sectors is relatively small. Thus, it is not expected that the inherent biases of job portals information considerably affect this study’s overall findings and conclusions.

3.2 Employer modelling Pipeline

Before proceeding to the machine learning phase, the collected data set was visually inspected to shape the target variables. A pattern emerged through visual inspection of the vacancy database, as illustrated in Figure 2. It became evident that certain employers only provided essential information about job requirements and necessary skills. However, another group of employers mentioned additional benefits that prospective candidates could expect. To name a few: “become a shareholder”, “free sport facilities to use”, “pension schemes”, “autonomy”, “support”, “training”, “safety at work”, “free snacks”, “mental therapist” and much more. Certainly not all, but out of many of the benefits mentioned, some could possibly be linked to the well-being aspect of a human-centric attitude towards an

employee and the work environment. Afterwards, these aspects can be compared to the academic perspective (see subsection 3.3 for methodology). As a result, we decided to focus primarily on the benefit sections of the job postings to explore potential connections to well-being.

Figure 2: A comparison of two job posting contents from two employers.

Notes: On the left, an employer states the requirements and job responsibilities, while on the right, an employer not only states the required skill set but commits to providing additional benefits to promote the well-being of the employee.

The data modelling pipeline was constructed using five layers of data extraction and processing steps. For a visual representation, please refer to Figure 3.

BM-401. Undoubtedly, the conventional NLP methods would face immense challenges in mining benefit data from job posting texts, primarily due to the intricate patterns and variations encountered in the text. The diversity of expressions used to convey benefits further exacerbates the difficulty, as there are countless ways in which benefits can be articulated. Thus, it was decided to work with the LLaMA LLMs and their derivatives. The LLaMA weights come in different sizes: 7B, 13B, 33B, and 65B parameters. In simple terms, the weights indicate how many configurable parameters were used in the training process of the models. The larger models exhibit higher accuracy but demand substantial computational power, which, unfortunately, comes at a significantly higher cost and is of limited

Figure 3: Machine learning methodology for mining and conceptualising the empirical image of well-being dimension using the job-posting data.

use for consumer devices. Luckily, a recent paper by Dettmers et al. (2022) has developed a quantisation mechanism that allows LLMs to be loaded onto consumer Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) with little to no effect on the models' ability to maintain accuracy. Nonetheless, through initial testing, it was quickly discovered that the original raw LLaMA weights of different sizes were inadequate to infer benefits. We believe this was because the raw weights were not fine-tuned for inference. Regrettably, achieving fine-tuning of the network would have demanded a substantial commitment of resources, including a minimum of six A100 GPUs for several months. Thus, a new route needed to be taken.

Instead, it was decided to tap into the derivatives of LLaMA that were provided by other researchers who had access to significant computing power. Some trialled models are: Alpaca, Koala, Blaze, Palmyra, Camel, GPT4All. The difference between these models and the raw LLaMA weights is that they were fine-tuned with clusters of GPUs for instruction and inference. This allowed for inference operations to be understood by LLM more accurately. Although the models performed better in the benefits mining task than the raw weights, the fine-tuned derivatives were unstable in their search for human-centricity for a consistent mining operation.

BM-402. As mentioned before, fully fine-tuning the network of LLM is, in most cases, not viable using consumer devices. However, an ingenious solution was presented by Zhang et al. (2023a), where Efficient Fine-tuning of Language Models with Zero-init Attention (LLaMA-Adapter) adds the learnable adaption prompts only to the topmost transformer layers. As a result, this reduces the number of trainable parameters and steers the model for better inference. To achieve this, a couple of thousand examples collected manually were given and trained on the Alpaca 13B model for several epochs, resulting in a more stable model.

It is important to understand that fine-tuning gives the LLM a framework to make a self-discovery of what empirical data might converge to after forming the boundaries of the search space. It does not command exact word matching but rather a conceptual search.

BM-404. The final result of the BM-40x layer was a list of over 500k raw human-centric associated phrases and sentences.

CL-501-504. The extracted phrases were further cleaned that resulted in short sentences of employers' benefits, like the following: "Catered lunch every day and regular drinks", "Company culture focused on the well-being and work-life balance", "Inclusive culture with progressive well-being support", "Fair employment practices" and so forth. However, by visually inspecting many phrases, many sen-

tences were either not very informative or were less meaningfully related to the well-being concept. Thus, it was decided to embed the 500k sentences using the 'all-MiniLM-L6-v2' model to a 768 dimensional dense vector space, later reduce its dimensions and use a cosine similarity for clustering. In the end, each sentence phrase was assigned to a certain cluster.

CL-601-604. In the second layer of clustering, the idea was to create topics for each cluster. Thus, the separately for each sentence phrase were vectored using the Term Frequency - Inverse Document Frequency (Tf-Idf) method and clustered using the k-means. Furthermore, the k-means centroids were ordered, and the eight closest distance points were selected to represent the topic of that cluster. As a result, each cluster had a topic assigned to them with eight words.

CL-701. The received 3811 cluster topics from CL-60x helped understand each cluster content. However, many duplicates and less meaningful phrases to human-centric dimension existed that needed to be removed. Thus, we attempted batch elimination by manually inspecting the topics that were not relevant, which resulted in 44k sentences. Afterwards, by sorting the received 44k topics, a clear pattern emerged that some keywords were solely health, finance or other topic-focused. Hence, it was decided to manually infer the over-arching dimensions that could group them from a macro level according to their meaning. Through careful examination, we were able to group all the topics effectively in the following seven higher dimensions that fully embraced the intended meanings of the topics and did not overlap excessively: A - self-realisation, B - empowerment and sustainability, C - infrastructure and safety, D - work-format, atmosphere, E - finance, F - health, nutrition, G - leisure, vacation. Further level details are outlined in the subsequent paragraphs.

CL-801-804. In the last part of clustering, all the previous cluster topics were deleted, and a double clustering was performed within those selected dimensions, e.g. clustering of sentences only within dimension A. By doing this, the algorithm had less noise to work with, and sub-dimensions can be further explored to

micro-levels. The double clustering worked similarly to before. First, the sentence embeddings were performed when clustered using k-means, and afterwards, using Tf-Idf vectorisation, cluster topics were created using the top 8 terms.

While conducting the clustering, deciding how granular the dimensions must be was important. As we aimed to generalise an employer's well-being perspective, we aimed for three levels. First, the L1 level is the over-arching level that describes a group of phrases at the highest levels where each L1 dimension was referenced with capital letters, e.g. A - self-realisation, B - empowerment, etc. Second, the level L2, within each L1 dimension, we attempted to group phrases into separate categories using respective capital letters and numbers, e.g. A1 - volunteer, A2 - family, B1 etc. Finally, level L3 had many topics within L2 levels and were named using capital letters and two numbers, e.g. A11. Differently, from the highest dimension topics that were manually inferred, the L3 dimension topics were auto-generated with keywords and were not edited. In the aftermath, each dimension had sentences with cluster numbers and cluster topics. Each cluster topic was assigned different levels of A, A1, and A11, and each level was given the appropriate topic name according to cluster topics.

3.3 Academia modelling pipeline and cross-validation

The collected phraseology in Section 3.2 offers valuable insights into the employer's viewpoint, potentially shedding light on their priorities. Nevertheless, it is vital to contrast how Industry 5.0 well-being concept realisation in academic literature differs from today's employers' viewpoint, emphasising the overlaps and gaps. By cross-validating, we can potentially construct a more comprehensive viewpoint that can help facilitate a dialogue about how the human-centered well-being concept should be embodied.

As such, it was decided to collect scientific papers mentioning Industry 5.0 and human-centricity keywords in the paper's title, abstract or keyword section, as

Figure 4: Academic well-being keyword retrieval pipeline

shown in Figure 4. This process led us to find a total of 72 articles. Afterwards, we retrieved all the textual information of the papers and again used LLM contextual search abilities to detect well-being related phraseology. The keyword extraction resulted in 271 well-being or human-centric related keywords. After removing the duplicates, we were left with 89 keywords.

Furthermore, in Section 3.2, the L1 dimensions were empirically generated solely for the employers' perspective, which might not encompass all the required dimensions for the academic part. To address this limitation, it was decided to adopt the Swarbrick and Yudof (2015) wellness model, which was built upon Hettler's wellness framework (Hettler, 1980) and has the following eight dimensions: emotional, physical, occupational, social, intellectual, environmental, financial spiritual. The decision to adopt the Swarbrick and Yudof (2015) wellness model over other frameworks was based on its comprehensiveness and alignment with the academic context. The model builds upon Hettler's wellness framework, which has been widely recognized and utilised for its holistic approach to well-being. By incorporating eight dimensions, this model covers a broad spectrum of aspects contributing to an individual's overall well-being.

As a result, the clustered employers' L2 dimensions were manually aligned with the most relevant dimensions in the Swarbrick wellness model, as was done for the academic phraseology. It is worth mentioning that the proposed framework has certain limitations as the lines between categories can become blurry at times and

may better fit one perspective than the other. They are also subject to interpreting what should be embodied by each category. Thus, if certain keywords had multiple meanings, they were distributed to more than one dimension. Nonetheless, the proposed framework provides structure and ensures a standardised evaluation, facilitating valuable insights into the potential overlaps and gaps between the academic and employers' viewpoints.

4 Results

4.1 Well-being through the eyes of an employer

The ML pipeline was deployed in May, and it took around 24 days to mine the full list of benefits for the BM-40x part. The clustering part was finished within one week, and most of the time was spent deciding the correct level names and their dependencies. Seven L1 dimensions were obtained, each having its own distinct characteristics and serving as placeholders for employers' expressed well-being benefits. The seven dimensions incorporate a plethora of diverse aspects of well-being, spanning from monetary and financial benefits to encompassing mind and body aspects like health, meditation, yoga, and purpose. In terms of size, the B - Self-realisation was the most varied dimension with 12053 sentence phrases in total. Then followed E - Monetary and D - Work-format, atmosphere dimensions with 6,409 and 5,758, respectively. The smallest one was C - equality, power, sustainability. While the keyword size does not definitively confirm that self-realisation virtues were the most important dimension among those gathered, its frequent appearance in many job postings does indicate that employers highly value and prioritise this dimension. See Figure 5 for a visual representation of each dimension.

The visualisation provided in Figure 5 concisely depicts the well-being dimensions from a macro point of view. However, for deeper understanding, it was decided to

Figure 5: Employer well-being dimension and its levels discovered using the job postings and machine learning pipeline.

Notes: Each dimension incorporates phrases employers use to signal certain values, benefits or virtues. L1 level consists of 7 dimensions, and L2 consists of 35 dimensions.

make a hierarchical graph along with a meta-table for each dimension, e.g. the self-realization dimension is represented by Table 1 and 2 and Figure 5. The purpose of the hierarchical graph is to offer insight into the dimension content, while the table acts as a further descriptor of what is recorded within the dimension. The numbers near the branches of hierarchical graphs represent employers' total count of sentence phrases. Each branch ends with a topic cluster example for that level. Meaningful work and self-realization play a crucial role in promoting well-being at the workplace. As found by Glavinska et al. (2020), self-realisation is a significant factor in forming individual components of psychological well-being. It could also act as a buffer against stress and increase work engagement, commitment, and job satisfaction (Allan et al., 2011; Blake et al., 2018).

Unsurprisingly, this dimension was reflected in job postings, where employers increasingly emphasise the alignment of individual passions, personal growth, and meaningful contributions within their organisations, as shown in Figure 6. On level A1, employers recognised the importance of volunteering work and fostered such behaviour by dedicating a certain amount of working hours to helping com-

munities, the environment and others in need of support. Most importantly, the companies paid the volunteering work at working hour rates. Research suggests that volunteering work can positively contribute to job meaningfulness and that the pull of meaningful volunteer work was even stronger when employees had less meaning in their jobs (Rodell, 2018).

Employers acknowledged the significance of prioritising family commitments and that family is pivotal for many individuals. Hence, the A2 level was incorporated into job postings to accommodate these needs. In Figure 6, we have established two important branches for the family (A2) level: support (A21) and atmosphere (A22). The prior was signalled through shared or paid maternity and parental leave opportunities. The leave benefits were also offered to be enhanced through increasing duration length and generous pay-outs in addition to the state compensations. Other ways of support offered were through on-site childcare, childcare on holidays, free childcare zones, parenting programs, domestic support, assurance of childcare costs, and toddler groups. Employers also signalled the general atmosphere supporting the family (see Table 1). Assistance with childcare and family leave policies have shown lower levels of role conflict and engagement in work and non-work domains Vaswani et al., 2001; Beauregard and Henry, 2009. There is also standing evidence of a spill-over effect from business to family and family to business. Glavinska et al., 2020. Dangerous loops can occur, where poor work-family balance induces conflicts in the family and conflicts in the family can further hurt work performance.

Figure 6: A hierarchical map of self-realisation dimension.

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Notes: The branch output, e.g. A111, depicts cluster topic centroids. The abbreviation of hid. refers to many hidden topics which are not possible to depict due to its large size.

The subsequent branch levels, A3 and A4, further embody the self-realisation dimension through impact and individuality. Research by Hu and Hirsh (2017) shows that workers are more likely to take lower pay when engaged in meaningful work. This evidence demonstrates the significant impact of work with a purpose on employee satisfaction and motivation. This meaningfulness concept was signalled by employers through phrases like positive impact on society, making an impact at your city, or role with impact for the A3 level.

Furthermore, on the A4 level, Individuality was signalled with phrases like plenty of room for your own creativity and initiative, space to develop oneself further, room to make choices within your own work, freedom to initiate changes and suggest new approaches, space and freedom to innovate and construct new ideas, freedom to implement best ideas. As discovered in the literature section, having a higher level of control of one's environment had a significantly better health outcome overall (Spell and Arnold, 2007; Karasek, 1990).

The A5 (opportunity to grow) and A6 (support) levels emphasise providing employees with opportunities for personal growth and showcasing how others can support their work. Personal growth has been linked to healthy workplace practices, better work satisfaction and less stress (Grawitch et al., 2006). Employers signalled their commitment to personal growth through offerings such as career and training opportunities, as well as providing free courses and seminars. In the career-focused A51 level, employers specifically highlight the existence of a career development path that can lead to advancement into more prominent positions within the company. Tangent to personal growth, level A6 offered other supporting mechanisms like the personal budget that can be individualised for training or mentorship programs. As reported by Wen et al. (2017), mentorship has been associated with higher levels of life satisfaction through psychological safety, while personalised budgets can help employees have more control over their careers.

Table 1: A – Self-realisation

L1	L2	L3	L3 Description	In sentence examples
A – Self realisation	A1 – Volunteer	A11 - Volunteer	Some employers had designated programs for volunteering work to help employees do valuable community work. Such activities are great for self-exploration and personal happiness. Most importantly, the volunteer work will be paid for by the company. Different volunteering schemes and programs exist.	- 24 hours per year that can be used for voluntary projects.-Paid volunteer work.- Three dedicated volunteer days. - Corporate volunteering hours.- Paid volunteering time (up to 16 hours per year).
		A21 – Support	Employers expressed support for job candidates with families. The support came in generous parental leaves, parental policies, child-care protection, subsidies for children, and childcare zones.	- Generous annual leave entitlement. - Child-care services for children aged 15 months to 6 years with ALPLA Kids. - Free childcare zone. - Annual leave of 4%.
	A2 – Family	A22 – Atmosphere	Another way family endorsement was signalled was through phrases promoting a family-friendly environment, culture, values, atmosphere, or even domestic support. Several companies went further and obtained certification as family-friendly organisations.	- Good family atmosphere - Family-like atmosphere and culture. - Domestic support. - Certified as a family-friendly company. - We swear by our family working atmosphere.
		A2 – Impact	A31 - Impact	Certain employers emphasised that work done within the company will not be mundane but will have a real impact that an employee could be proud of. In turn, this can contribute to self-realisation and a deep sense of fulfilment at the workplace.

Table 2: A – Self-realisation (Cont.)

L1	L2	L3	L3 Description	In sentence examples
A – Self realisation	A4 – Individuality	A41 – You and Yourself	Job postings prioritise creativity, freedom, and innovative thinking. Opportunities to implement innovative ideas, and even encourages questioning and improving existing practices.	- Space for creativity and open to further developments. - Creative and challenge the status quo by bringing new ideas. - Open to hearing and implementing new ideas.
		A42 – Recognition	Employers proposed various initiatives such as award ceremonies, schemes, and programs to ensure employees feel valued and appreciated for sharing their ideas.	- Handsomely rewarded. - Recognition awards. - Recognition of efforts and contribution. - Global awards and nominations. - Peer recognition and rewards programs.
	A5 – Opportunity to grow	A51 – Career and Training	Job postings emphasised career progression and training opportunities. Employers highlighted the existence of career advancement paths, allowing employees to grow and avoid being stagnant in one position. They highlighted the importance of training activities supported by personal budgets or organised by the company, encouraging applicants to pursue further training.	- Continuous development opportunities and a personal training budget. - Training is fully funded as part of the work-study program. - Professional training and education. - Diverse training and development opportunities within the company. - Opportunity for career advancement advice and guidance. - Career development and progression opportunities
		A52 – Courses and Seminars	To achieve personal growth, seminars and courses will be provided that are paid for by the companies.	- Sponsored online courses. - Training courses offered by the company. - The possibility of following courses and training.
	A6 – Support	A61 - Budget	The growth support was also provided in the form of a budget form the employers that allow employees to choose their own path of development rather than taking firms organised courses.	- Personal learning budget (2000 Eur/year). - Visa sponsorship. - Budget for professional development. - Budget for the employee’s education.
		A62 - Assistance	Employers mentioned mentorship, guidance, resource groups, and networking to support employees. They emphasise leveraging top performers’ expertise and experience to benefit newcomers joining the company.	- Access to an employee assistance program. - Employee resource groups for networking and support. - Opportunity to network with like-minded individuals. - Coaching from experienced developers, where necessary. - Mentoring assistance from a senior member of staff.

A subsequent important dimension is empowerment and sustainability, as depicted in Figure 7. Here lies an important principle of equality in terms of age, race, gender and other aspects (see B1 in Figure 7). Employers expressed a deep commitment to eradicating discrimination in their hiring practices and are dedicated to fostering a work environment that values diversity and inclusivity, which has a strong impact on the overall well-being (Wilks and Neto, 2013). Furthermore, the absence of privacy has been identified as contributing to increased stress, primarily due to environmental control mechanisms that can influence stress levels (Veitch, 2011). Employers signalled the care for privacy through confidentiality measures on level B2.

Employers have also tried to express whether they are aligned with socially responsible policies and sustainability practices on level B3. A study by (Ahmad et al., 2023) has linked corporate social responsibility negatively related to employee burnout, thus enhancing the well-being component. Certain reports by WEF (2021) also raise attention that employees suffer from eco-anxiety (extreme worry about current and future harm to the environment caused by human activity and climate change) and view sustainable companies more favourably.

From an employers' perspective, the resilience aspect at a workplace was understood as a means of ensuring job security and future-proof employment for an employee. Research indicates that job security positively affects the well-being of an employee (Abdelmotaleb and Saha, 2013; Green and Leeves, 2013). In addition, certain employers preferred flat hierarchy lines, open communication and short decision lines to empower the worker and offered union support when negotiating salaries (see levels B5 and B6). The latter was signalled through phrases like "short communication lines with staff and managers", "flat organisation structure", "salary in accordance to collective agreement". Evidence suggests that preventing staff from speaking their mind can stop companies from achieving their strategic goals and make them feel less valued, while weak salary negotiation positions can create negative well-being effects (Parke and Seo, 2001; Haddon, 2018;

Bryson et al., 2013).

Figure 7: A hierarchical map of empowerment and sustainability dimension.

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Notes: The numbers near the levels represent the number of sentences or expressions recorded for that level. The branch output, e.g. B111, depicts cluster topic centroids. The abbreviation of hid. Refers to many hidden topics that are impossible to depict due to its large size.

The third discovered dimension was related to infrastructure and safety (see Appendix A²). Sustaining physical damage due to equipment-related incidents has severe negative side effects on one’s mental health. Thus, employers explicitly stated their commitment to compliance with safety regulations, affirming their dedication to following established safety protocols and regulations on level C4 (Grawitch et al., 2006). In addition, much attention was paid to work-space location and reachability. Evidence suggests that long-commuting times and no parking might hinder certain aspects of well-being (Iftikhar, 2017). Employers also offered climate-friendly mobility with bikes and ticket schemes. Furthermore, a recent study has shown that rental and other housing costs can have an extreme financial burden on one’s mental health (Shamsuddin and Campbell, 2022). Thus, accommodation benefits employers provide on level C2 can have a life-changing effect. Similarly, companies highlighted that they would provide necessary equipment for work, from phones and laptops to transportation.

Employers were also considerate regarding work arrangement issues and atmosphere (see Appendix B). Much attention was paid to remote work and on-site options. Evidence is complicated whether remote or in-office work is better for the well-being. (Chevtaeva et al., 2023; Fan and Moen, 2023). Likewise, the studies have mixed results regarding flexible work, scheduling, and finishing tasks according to one’s timetables (Hartner-Tiefenthaler et al., 2023). Nonetheless, having options is preferable, and employers were willing to accommodate these needs on D1 to D5 levels.

The epitome of stress often concerns financial situations (Mensah et al., 2023; Baquero, 2023). As shown in appendix C, to soften the burden, employers signalled various schemes for how employees can benefit from their financial circumstances through remunerations, reimbursements, and bonuses. Certain companies were

²To accommodate the extensive number of dimensions identified on the employer side, it was decided to put the hierarchical graphs in the appendix and to omit the descriptive tables of each dimension. This does not imply that one dimension holds more value than others, but rather, it is a measure taken to prevent the paper from becoming excessively lengthy

eager to share profits and provided financial guidance to assist with money management, savings, and utilising tax benefits. Employers were also eager to think long-term and provided pension schemes and payment frequency options for struggling individuals.

A considerable amount of attention in the job postings was also paid to the health amenities and nutrition (see Appendix D). Affordable healthcare can contribute to subjective well-being. Thus, employers were eager to suggest health plans and insurance schemes (Kim, 2021). Furthermore, the importance of disability accommodation was prominently emphasised, as shown in Appendix D, level F31. Moreover, evidence suggests employers can meaningfully contribute to work-life benefits through their policies, fitness facilities and programs, and wellness programs (Beauregard and Henry, 2009; Sirgy, 2018; Sakuraya A., 2022). In response, employers were willing to adopt proactive measures by hiring company doctors and providing accessible mental health support services.

On the F6 level, employers offered various meal discounts by giving restaurant vouchers or tickets. Employees can access a broader range of choices through meal subsidies. It incentivises employees to take regular breaks from work, fostering opportunities for socialising and team building. In addition, when all employees can afford various foods, it promotes a sense of equality within the workplace. Furthermore, although subsidising certain aspects of foods and activities is beneficial, some employers were eager to provide free meal and drink experiences, see level F5.

Last but not least is the leisure and vacation dimension. Balancing work, having time off, and relaxing with co-workers or friends helps prevent burnout and reduces stress and exhaustion. Employees can prioritise self-care through exercise, nutrition and sufficient rest (?) when given personal time. The latter also compensates unsatisfactory activities within work with satisfactory activities outside, thus keeping a healthy mind balanced (Sirgy, 2002). Most importantly, there is a limit to a person's satisfaction from one domain. Thus, being involved in other life

activities is useful for an employee to stay focused, positive and productive (Sirgy, 2018; Diener and Tov, 2008).

The employers signalled such relaxation and leisure activities in the job postings depicted in Appendix E. On the G1 level, employers aimed to provide discounts on sports and other fitness activities. The latter can help deal with stress and reduce the chances of over-burning (Sakuraya A., 2022). As depicted in level G2, employers in the job postings descriptions promised team events, adventures, BBQ parties, hiking, sports games like darts, soccer, karting, cultural outings, employee parties and other recreational activities. Likewise, the purpose of level G23 is to provide infrastructure for such activities.

Concerning the G3 level, two types of time-offs were detected. First, conventional holidays/vacations are legally binding to state law, but their conditions vary as employers can address the bare minimum requirements or be more generous. This category includes flexible vacation schedules, school closing days, replacement opportunities, attractive holidays in the company's resorts and other holiday entitlements. In addition, certain employers have implemented unlimited holiday schemes, wherein employees who efficiently complete their required tasks are granted the flexibility to take additional vacations. This benefit may not be viable for many professions, but this could be an invaluable proposition for certain specialists who can automate workflows. On the other hand, differently from conventional vacations, some firms provided additional rest days, see level G32, in various forms: free day from work on birthdays, the possibility to have a four-week day, extra days off, Monday rest day, ability to buy extra holidays, purchase extra leave and much more. These small conveniences amplify personal autonomy, enhancing subjective well-being (Wheatley, 2017).

To sum up, the development of the ML pipeline based on LLM marked a significant step forward in uncovering the dimensions of employers' expressed well-being benefits, which would otherwise be too complex to detect and analyse via other means. These findings provide a comprehensive picture of the dimensions that

shape employers' perspectives on well-being, laying the foundation for a more holistic understanding of Industry 5.0 workplaces.

4.2 Quantifying Human-Centricity in Job Posts

After identifying the possible patterns associated with well-being and constructing clusters, we estimated the percentage of UK vacancies that explicitly referenced any identified patterns. Figure 8 depicts the distribution of vacancies mentioning pattern-related across the seven macro dimensions highlighted in subsection 4.1. Among these dimensions, A-self-realisation stands out as the most commonly mentioned (46%), followed by D-Work-format, atmosphere (39%), and E-Finance dimension (19%). In contrast, the least frequently mentioned dimension is B-Empowerment, sustainability, and C-Infrastructure, safety accounting for only 6% and 13% of the total vacancies, respectively.

Figure 8: Share of vacancies by dimensions - L1

Source: Vacancy data. Own calculations.

Figure 8 illustrates the prevalence of sub-dimensions at L2 level mentioned in UK job vacancies. Approximately 36% of the vacancies refer to patterns related to the A51-career training sub-dimension. This particular sub-dimension stands out as the most frequent one because job vacancies in the UK commonly mention some training opportunities will be provided at the beginning of the job. The D42-caring sub-dimension is also frequently mentioned in job vacancies. Employers frequently mention phrases such as “supportive team”, “friendly team”, “team lead”, and “teamwork”, among others. Thus, this evidence confirms that self-realisation (via offering training opportunities) and Work-format (via offering a friendly/team environment) are prioritised by employers to attract job seekers.

Importantly, the data reveals that around 27% of job vacancies in the UK did not explicitly mention any terms or patterns associated with well-being from the dictionary. This finding highlights that for a substantial portion of employers, the human-centric aspect of well-being may not be a prominent consideration when posting job advertisements. This insight offers valuable implications for understanding the priorities and perspectives of employers regarding employee well-being in the job market.

4.3 Cross-validating employers dictionary with the academic syllabus

The collected clusters of keywords in section 4.1 are an important part of understanding the employers' well-being perspective. However, it is crucial to cross-validate the L2 dimensions with the academic literature to determine whether all L2 clusters can genuinely be regarded as integral components of Industry 5.0 well-being. Table 3 depicts the academic and employers' phraseology according to the Swarbrick and Yudof (2015) eight-dimensional well-being model (See Section 3.3).

The comparison table corroborates that the dimensions identified in Section 4.1 are aligned with the evidence provided by the literature. However, it also sheds light on a crucial aspect of well-being that academia might have overlooked. For instance, academics have emphasised that, on the emotional level, a worker in Industry 5.0 should be associated with feelings of health and safety. Considerable emphasis was placed on mental health, recognising that working with machines can sometimes lead to feelings of loneliness. Burnout and other psychological disorders were also mentioned as many technologies anchor Industry 5.0 workers to be connected to technology 24/7. Most importantly, a generally positive attitude and personal happiness should be at the core (Rožanec et al., 2022; Kaasinen et al., 2022; Cillo et al., 2022).

In parallel, from an employers' perspective, the mental health issues were addressed through mental aid resources, counselling and other support measures (see F4). A positive working environment and attitudes were encouraged on the D6 level. Differently from academia, employers recognise the need for family emotional support on level A2, which considerably influences the overall mental well-being of the worker. However, academia recognised the danger of unethical use of wearable devices that might cause emotional stress of being constantly monitored, which was lacking on the employers' side.

On the physical level, the health of an operator was mentioned in different journals,

suggesting following occupational safety guidelines and taking precautionary measures for burnouts (Tran et al., 2022; Cillo et al., 2022; Orso et al., 2022). On the other hand, many employers have also communicated strong values of promoting and sustaining workers' health through healthcare plans, insurance schemes, and health promotion. They also emphasised nutrition, one of the most important elements of sustaining people's health. The latter part was lacking in the academic literature. Employers also addressed physical burnout by offering adequate rest days and vacation schemes.

The occupational dimension was the most widely covered category by academics and employers. Researchers acknowledged that Industry 5.0 workplace should promote continuous learning, have flexible work, good work-life balance, respect, reward, and empower its employees as well as work itself needs to be fulfilling and meaningful (Tran et al., 2022; Leng et al., 2022). Most of the latter aspects have been addressed by employers in their own way, but other important considerations for human-centric workplace is that work spaces and equipment should be easily accessible and designed to inspire productivity and motivation. However, one missing component on the employers' side was the proactive human-robot collaboration that can contribute to the worker's well-being.

On the social level, academia highlighted the importance of community well-being, social relationships, issues and responsibility (Gomathi et al., 2023; Carayannis et al., 2023). Hence, the volunteering work offered by employers and strong work environment support from colleagues with off-work team activities, can create a better social foundation for a worker to thrive in Industry 5.0. Both parties admit that social life outside work should be another vital component in the social category and put forward the importance of diversity and equality in the workplace and outside.

From an academic standpoint, the significance of lifelong learning, personal growth, and intellectual development cannot be overstated in achieving a human-centric workforce in the intellectual category (Leng et al., 2022; Tóth et al., 2023). Here

Table 3: Cross-validating human-centric well-being findings in academic literature with employers perspective

	Academia	Employer
Emotional	Satisfaction; Feeling safe; Feeling healthy; Feeling well surrounded; Resilience; Positive attitude; Psychological effects; Personal preferences; Psychological disorder; Respect; Happiness; Mental well-being; Burnout; Data Security; Ethical considerations of wearable self-tracking device;	F4 – Overall wellness, D6 - attitude, A2 – family, B2 - privacy
Physical	Safety; Ergonomic; Bad postures; Musculoskeletal disorders; Health; Healthy operator 4.0; Ergonomic risks; Physical health; Hygiene; Safety measures; Perceived stress level; Posture; Physical fatigue; Health-related quality of life; Occupational safety and health; Burnout; Work-life conflict; Job autonomy; Privacy;	C13 - State, F1 – health plans, F2 – health insurance, F3 – health accommodation, F4 – Overall wellness, F5 – catered foods and drinks, F6 – discounts (meals), G3 – time off.
Occupational	Collaboration; Flexibility; Continuous learning; Lifelong learning; Empowerment; Workplace learning; Fulfilling and rewarding jobs; Workforce flexibility; Work-life balance; Transformational leadership; Employee retention; Respect, Valued, Resilience; Organisational climate; Employee voice; Non-discrimination, and Fairness, Proactive human-robot collaboration for well-being; Autonomy; Privacy;	A3 - impact; A4 – individuality; B2 - privacy; B4 - resilience, B5 – communication & hierarchies, B6 – negotiation power, C1 – workspace, C3 – equipment, C4 – safety, D1 – remote work, D2 - on-site work, D3 – travel, D4 – flexibility, D5 – work-forms, D6 – attitude, D7 – environment, G3 – time off.
Social	Social cohesion; Social exclusion; Social responsibility; social determinants of health; Community well-being; Social care issues; Inclusion; Relationship; Diversity; Communication; Participation; Work-life balance; Social/emotional context	A1 – volunteer; A6 – support, B1 – equality, G1 – Leisure discounts, G2 – Leisure activities, A2 – family, A3 - impact;
Intellectual	Lifelong learning; immersive learning; Self-actualisation; Proactive human-robot collaboration for well-being; Workplace learning; Continuous innovation; Motivation; Autonomy;	A3 - impact; A4 – individuality; A5 – opportunity to grow; A6 – support, D6 - attitude
Environmental	Environmental responsibility; Sustainability; Environmental sustainability; Smart, sustainable, and inclusive solutions; Eco-friendly behaviors; Sustainable supply chains; Sustainable societies; Sustainable digital transition; Eco-innovation;	B3 – sustainability,
Financial	Financial performance; Prosperity; Profitability; Economic challenges; Financial well-being; Economic well-being; Social welfare	E1 – remuneration plans, E2 – stakeholder, E3 – reimbursements, E4 – welfare.
Spiritual		

Notes: The eight wellness dimensions are architected by Swarbrick and Yudof (2015)

again, the pro-active collaboration with robots can help humans accelerate their journey to personal development, which was missing on the employers' side Leng et al. (2022).

The sustainability aspect was covered by both parties in terms of producing sustainable products that are important for a healthy environment ecosystem to thrive. On the financial side, academics emphasised the ongoing social issues concerning the economic challenges and social welfare (Saniuk et al., 2022). As a counter to that, employers suggested many savings, pension, and financial reimbursement schemes. Most importantly, a common theme for Industry 5.0 was moving from shareholder to stakeholder. Hence, the share options employers provide could help employees be more invested in the company. Lastly, spiritual well-being has not been explored by either group.

5 Discussion

The discourse unfolding around human-centricity in Industry 5.0 is highly complex and nuanced. For one, it seems that the interpretation of human-centricity has many perspectives yet to be settled in a clear consensus. There has been a strong technological push where humans are envisioned to collaborate closely with robots or even merge with artificial intelligence through implanted chips. However, it is also important not to lose track of the problems in Industry 4.0, which should be continuously addressed in Industry 5.0. Industry 4.0 has raised many concerns about an employee's well-being, income and social inequalities that have begun to occur due to robotisation and automation in factory settings (Lee and Lim, 2021). As of now, it is unclear whether the human-robot collaboration will exacerbate the ongoing issues further or will truly help workers to be more satisfied with their lives and prospects.

In our analysis, we explored both academic literature and gathered data from various employers, aiming to shed light on ongoing social topics. More precisely, we measure the current state of employers' perspective on the employees' well-being and explore how well-being has emerged in academic circles in the context of human-centricity. Results indicate that the focus on workers' wellness is not frequently mentioned in the job vacancies; instead, it appears to be a byproduct of other organisational priorities. For instance, the L2 mapping procedure highlights that the training dimension has been the top priority for employers. This evidence aligns with the trends observed in Industry 4.0, where there is a strong emphasis on enhancing workers' productivity and placing significant demands on them for continuous, non-stop learning.

On the positive side, the training opportunities can make an employee more resilient and aid in their personal development. However, even in such cases, the training L2 dimension has only been detected in less than 47% of job postings, whilst other dimensions, except work format, barely crossed or were under 20%

threshold. Even more worrying is the fact that around 27% of the job, ads did not mention any of the 44k thousand keywords related to an employee's well-being. It is unclear if such companies had no intentions to support an employee's well-being or did not explicitly mention those intentions.

On the academic front, the well-being discussion has only been touched on the surface, as most of the Industry 5.0 papers exploring the human-centricity concept focused on how robotics will be integrated with humans in the loop. Hence, ergonomics of postural risk and general safety have been raised. While there are some references to well-being as a general concept, a comprehensive and nuanced exploration of how the well-being approach should differ in Industry 5.0 to prevent the exacerbation of social issues witnessed in Industry 4.0 remains largely unexplored. Many keywords discovered were loosely placed within the text without further analysis.

In light of these findings, we urge to sharpen the discussion of well-being within Industry 5.0 by not only including the human-robot collaboration aspect but the wellness of the employee as well, transitioning from solely productivity benefits for factories to a balanced work-life philosophy. This approach envisions a workforce where employees are not only merged with cyber and artificial intelligence technologies but are also personally satisfied, healthy, and engaged in meaningful workplace work. For a visual representation, Figure 10 depicts how the notion of well-being can fit in explaining some portion of the human-centricity concept. If we consider all the circles as the entirety of the human-centricity explanation, the well-being of an employee should be an integral component that overlaps within many perspectives, possibly more than three.

Within the Figure 10 framework, different actors can meaningfully contribute to the worker's well-being with different means: employers can implement a wide range of policies, some of which have been gathered and depicted here in L1 and L2 levels in Figure 5, academics should further draw attention that human-robot collaboration not only can increase the productivity but there are at least eight other

Figure 10: A conceptual understanding of Industry 5.0 human-centricity dimensions.

well-being dimensions where artificial intelligence and robotics can contribute to increasing workers life satisfaction. Lastly, there should be a strong representation of an employee’s side of how they envision the future of the workplace.

Thus, promoting the transition from Industry 4.0 to 5.0 requires a paradigm shift in how employers perceive and prioritise their workforce’s well-being. Policymakers play a crucial role in driving this change by fostering awareness and understanding among employers about the importance of valuing workers’ wellness in the context of Industry 5.0.

Policymakers can launch awareness campaigns and initiatives to highlight the benefits of a well-being-centric work environment. These efforts should emphasise the positive impact of employee well-being on productivity, creativity, and overall organisational performance. By showcasing success stories and best practices of companies that have integrated well-being into their core values, policymakers can inspire and encourage other employers to follow suit.

One of the key insights from our research is that the training dimension has been the top priority for employers. Policymakers can use this information to design

targeted support and incentives for training and development programs. By investing in these initiatives, policymakers can foster a work environment that not only enhances the skills and capabilities of the workforce but also prioritises employee well-being and job satisfaction.

Furtermore, policymakers should use the data-driven decision-making approach by analysing job vacancies to inform their policies and strategies. By understanding how well-being is reflected in job advertisements, they can tailor interventions to address specific gaps and challenges in promoting a healthier and more human-centric work environment.

Collaboration with academic institutions is crucial to further explore the link between well-being and human-centricity in the context of Industry 5.0. By working with researchers and experts, policymakers can develop evidence-based policies that effectively address the well-being needs of the workforce. This partnership can lead to innovative and comprehensive approaches to promoting employees' well-being and fostering a thriving workforce in the era of Industry 5.0.

Additionally, LLM-based methodologies open up the opportunity to explore more aspects of job vacancies and their relations with other variables. Future research can delve into identifying the specific types of jobs (occupations/sectors) that are more likely to offer human-centric benefits to potential employees. This deeper analysis will provide valuable insights into the industries and roles that prioritise employee well-being and can contribute to shaping a more human-centric workplace culture.

While vacancy data has proven to be a valuable and well-established source of information for understanding employers' perspectives, it is also essential to consider other sources. Contract agreements, for instance, could offer valuable insights into the intricacies of implementing Industry 5.0 practices within organisations. Analysing these agreements could provide a deeper understanding of how different firms are embracing human-centricity and making Industry 5.0 a reality. More-

over, many other aspects warrant exploration. One such area of investigation could focus on understanding how productivity gains can be achieved by automating specific tasks while simultaneously enhancing and retraining the remaining human workforce.

Finally, this research is not exempt from limitations. Despite having collected over 1.8 million job vacancies and most academic papers on human-centricity, we admit that certain research limitations exist. For starters, not all employers are willing to disclose all the well-being benefits on the job platforms. Hence, the benefit mapping results can have variations. Creating attractive and professional job ads is a skill of its own. Thus, lacking the necessary knowledge and talent may influence the job description content. Second, the geographical region selected concerned only the UK data. Thus, a country bias might exist. Third, academic circles have just started to accelerate Industry 5.0 research. It is still early to judge the academic point of view and whether social issues will be fully addressed in the future. Lastly, the LLM modelling style is still a new method that needs to be improved on its own. The conceptual search is intriguing but can also contain errors whether used for the vacancy or academic modelling. The same thing applies to clustering algorithms, which may not capture meaning adequately and group things incorrectly. Nonetheless, we have demonstrated that without the need for a dictionary, it is possible to build a well-being taxonomy on its own.

6 Conclusion

Our research aims to advance the understanding of Industry 5.0 by introducing an innovative AI-based approach. The creation of comprehensive pattern identification and clustering of employer keywords, along with its validation against academic perspectives, forms the foundation of our unique methodology. We have demonstrated that with the use of LLM, it is possible to address the challenges associated with measuring and mapping complex terms/patterns, such as well-being in the workplace. Specifically, we have demonstrated the effectiveness of LLM in identifying various labour market characteristics without relying on a pre-defined dictionary. LLM's ability to grasp human language's context, subtleties, and nuances minimises the chances of misinterpreting data. As a result, LLM opens up new possibilities for developing and improving labour market taxonomies and accurately identifying different dimensions in large datasets like vacancy data.

Our research contributes to enhancing data analysis in the context of Industry 5.0, providing valuable insights into the well-being aspects of the workforce and facilitating informed decision-making in this dynamic field. Through empirical analysis, we shed light on the well-being aspect of human-centricity from the employer's viewpoint using vacancy data.

The data-driven approach reveals seven human-centric dimensions from the employers' perspective. Most of these dimension overlaps with academia, but there are also gaps. For instance, Employers highlight the need for family emotional support, which considerably influences the overall mental well-being of the worker, while academia points to the danger of unethical use of wearable devices that might cause emotional stress of being constantly monitored, which was lacking in the employers' side. As a result, this research opens up opportunities to bridge these gaps and create a more comprehensive understanding of human-centricity in the context of well-being and Industry 5.0 workplaces.

The data analysis showed that self-realisation (via offering training opportunities)

and Work-format (via offering a friendly/team environment) are prioritised by employers to attract job seekers. However, a considerable share of employers may not see it relevant to emphasise well-being conditions to attract potential workers explicitly. This evidence suggests the need for greater awareness and attention to employee well-being across the board. Organisations may benefit from implementing well-being initiatives and communicating them effectively to attract and retain top talent in an increasingly competitive labour market.

Our data-driven approach to understanding well-being using vacancy data showcases the importance of harnessing technology and data in policymaking. Policymakers can explore innovative ways to collect and analyse data to gain deeper insights into workforce trends and needs. These new analysis methods can inform evidence-based policymaking, leading to more effective and targeted interventions to support the workforce. As Industry 5.0 continues to evolve, policymakers must stay vigilant to address the potential challenges and risks associated with the increasing use of technology in the workplace. Furthermore, policymakers can devise strategies to provide support and resources to workers facing these challenges and promote work-life balance in the digital era.

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A Appendix

Figure 11: Hierarchical map of the empowerment and sustainability dimension. **Note.** The numbers near the levels represent the number of sentences or expressions recorded for that level. The branch output, e.g., C111, depicts cluster topic centroids. The abbreviation of hid. refers to many hidden topics, which are not possible to depict due to their large size.

B Appendix

Figure 12: Hierarchical map of the empowerment and sustainability dimension. **Note.** The numbers near the levels represent the number of sentences or expressions recorded for that level. The branch output, e.g., D111, depicts cluster topic centroids. The abbreviation of hid. refers to many hidden topics, which are not possible to depict due to their large size.

C Appendix

Figure 13: Hierarchical map of the empowerment and sustainability dimension. **Note.** The numbers near the levels represent the number of sentences or expressions recorded for that level. The branch output, e.g., E111, depicts cluster topic centroids. The abbreviation of hid. refers to many hidden topics, which are not possible to depict due to their large size.

D Appendix

Figure 14: Hierarchical map of the health and nutrition dimension. **Note.** The numbers near the levels represent the number of sentences or expressions recorded for that level. The branch output, e.g., F111, depicts cluster topic centroids. The abbreviation of hid. refers to many hidden topics, which are not possible to depict due to their large size.

E Appendix

Figure 15: Hierarchical map of the health and nutrition dimension. **Note.** The numbers near the levels represent the number of sentences or expressions recorded for that level. The branch output, e.g., F111, depicts cluster topic centroids. The abbreviation of hid. refers to many hidden topics, which are not possible to depict due to their large size.